

Search strategy in MEDLINE via Ovid SP

1. "Schizophrenia Spectrum and Other Psychotic Disorders"/ or exp Schizophrenia/ or Affective Disorders, Psychotic/ or exp Psychotic Disorders/ or (Psychoses or Psychosis or Psychotic* or Antipsychotic* or Schizoaffective or Schizo-Affective or Schizophreni* or Schizophreniform or Schizotyp*).ti,ab,tw.
2. "(4-(m-Chlorophenylcarbamoyloxy)-2-butynyl)trimethylammonium Chloride"/ or Bethanechol/ or Bethanechol Compounds/ or Methacholine Chloride/ or Oxotremorine/ or Pilocarpine/ or Arecoline/ or Strychnine/ or Vincamine/ or Clozapine/ or ("(-)-aceclidine" or "(-)-eburnamonine" or "(-)-YM796" or "(+)-aceclidine" or "(+/-)YM796" or "(11C)butylthio-TZTP" or "(2 acetoxyethyl)trimethylammonium chloride" or "(2 acetyllactoyloxyethyl)trimethylammonium 1,5 naphthalenedisulfonate" or "(2 benzilyloxyethyl)dimethylethylammonium chloride" or "(2 hydroxyethyl)nicotinamide nitrate" or "(2 hydroxyethyl)trimethyl ammonium chloride carbamate" or "(2 hydroxypropyl)trimethylammonium chloride acetate" or "(2 hydroxypropyl)trimethylammonium chloride carbamate" or "(3H)PT-1284" or "(3-O-hexyloxy)-TZTP" or "(4-(m-Chlorophenylcarbamoyloxy)-2-butynyl)trimethylammonium Chloride" or "(acetyllactoyl)choline 1,5 naphthalenedisulfonate" or "(S)-2-ethyl-8-methyl-1-thia-4,8-diazaspiro(4.5)decan-3-one" or "[11C]butylthio-TZTP" or "[11C]xanomeline" or "[18F]FP-TZTP" or "[3H]acetylcholine" or "[3H]dimethyl-W84" or "[4 [(3 chlorophenyl)carbamoyloxy] 2 butynyl]trimethylammonium" or "[4 [(4 chlorophenyl)carbamoyloxy] 2 butynyl]trimethylammonium iodide" or "1 (2 chloromethyl 1 pyrrolidinyl) 4 (2 oxo 1 pyrrolidinyl) 2 butyne" or "1 (2 oxo 1 pyrrolidinyl) 4 (1 pyrrolidinyl) 2 butyne" or "1 (2 oxopyrrolidin 1 yl) 4 (pyrrolidin 1 yl)but 2 yne" or "1 (2 oxopyrrolidino) 4 pyrrolidino 2 butyne" or "1 (2 pyrimidyl)piperazine" or "1 (2,2 diphenyl 3 oxolanyl) n,n dimethylmethanamine" or "1 (2,2 diphenyloxolan 3 yl) n,n dimethylmethanamine" or "1 (2,2 diphenyltetrahydro 3 furanyl) n,n dimethylmethanamine" or "1 (2,2 diphenyltetrahydrofuran 3 yl) n,n dimethylmethanamine" or "1 (2,4 dimethyl 5,7 dihydro 6h pyrrolo[3,4 b]pyridin 6 yl) 2 [1 [2 (trifluoromethyl) 4 pyridinyl] 3 azetidyl]ethanone" or "1 (2,4 dimethyl 5,7 dihydro 6h pyrrolo[3,4 b]pyridin 6 yl) 2 [1 [2 (trifluoromethyl)pyridin 4 yl]azetid 3 yl]ethan 1 one" or "1 (2,4 dimethyl 5,7 dihydropyrrolo[3,4 b]pyridin 6 yl) 2 [1 [2 (trifluoromethyl) 4 pyridinyl] 3 azetidyl]ethanone" or "1 (2,4 dimethyl 5,7 dihydropyrrolo[3,4 b]pyridin 6 yl) 2 [1 [2 (trifluoromethyl)pyridin 4 yl]azetid 3 yl]ethan 1 one" or "1 (4 trimethylammonio 2 butyn 1 yl) 2 pyrrolidinone" or "1 (4 trimethylammonio 2 butynyl) 2 pyrrolidinone" or "1 (4 trimethylammonio 2 butynyl) 2 pyrrolidinone iodide" or "1 (5,7 dihydro 2,4 dimethyl 6h pyrrolo[3,4 b]pyridin 6 yl) 2 [1 [2 (trifluoromethyl) 4 pyridinyl] 3 azetidyl]ethanone" or "1 (5,7 dihydro 2,4 dimethyl 6h pyrrolo[3,4 b]pyridin 6 yl) 2 [1 [2 (trifluoromethyl)pyridin 4 yl]azetid 3 yl]ethan 1 one" or "1 (5,7 dihydro 2,4 dimethylpyrrolo[3,4 b]pyridin 6 yl) 2 [1 [2 (trifluoromethyl) 4 pyridinyl] 3 azetidyl]ethanone" or "1 (5,7 dihydro 2,4 dimethylpyrrolo[3,4 b]pyridin 6 yl) 2 [1 [2 (trifluoromethyl)pyridin 4 yl]azetid 3 yl]ethan 1 one" or "1 [4 (2 chloromethyl 1 pyrrolidinyl) 2 butynyl] 2 pyrrolidone" or "1 [4 (n acetyl n methylamino) 2 pentyn 1 yl]pyrrolidine" or "1 [4 [(2 chloroethyl)methylamino] 2 butynyl] 2 pyrrolidinone" or "1 methyl 1,2,5,6 tetrahydroisonicotinic acid" or "1-((1H-Indazol-5-yl)sulfonyl)-N-ethyl-N-(2-(trifluoromethyl)benzyl)piperidine-4-carboxamide" or "1-(4-methoxybenzyl)-4-oxo-1,4-dihydroquinoline-3-carboxylic acid" or "1-(4-methoxybenzyl)-5-(trifluoromethoxy)indoline-2,3-dione" or "1,2,5,6 tetrahydro 1 methyl 3 pyridinecarboxaldehyde o methyloxime" or "1,2,5,6 tetrahydro 1 methylisonicotinic acid" or "1,3-bis(4-(phthalimidomethoxyiminomethyl)pyridinium-1-yl)propane" or "1,3-bis(4-(phthalimidomethoxyimino-methyl)pyridinium-1-yl)propane dibromide" or "1,4,5,6 tetrahydro 5 phenoxyprymidine" or "1,4-bis(3-((3-azabicyclo(2.2.2)octanyl)-1,2,5-

Muscarinic receptor agonists and positive allosteric modulators in animal models of psychosis: a systematic review and metaanalysis
Search strategy in MEDLINE via Ovid SP

thiadiazol-4-yloxy)-1-propyn-1-yl)benzene" or "1,4-bis(3--((3-azabicyclo(2.2.2)octanyl)-1,2,5-thiadiazol-4-yloxy)-1-propyn-1-yl)benzene 2-tartrate" or "1,6-hexamethylenebis(dimethyl(3-phthalimidopropyl)ammonium bromide]" or "10,11-dimethoxystrychnine" or "13alpha ethyl 2,3,5,6,12,13,13a,13b octahydro 12 hydroxy 1h indolo[3,2,1 de]pyrido[3,2,1 ij][1,5]naphthyridine 12 carboxylic acid methyl ester" or "14-oxoeburnane" or "14,15 dihydro 14beta hydroxy (3alpha,16alpha) eburnamenine 14 carboxylic acid methyl ester" or "16 ethyl 14 oxopyridocantione" or "16 oxoeburnane" or "17alpha ethynyl 17beta hydroxy 5alpha androstano[3,2 b]pyrimido[1,2 a]benzimidazole" or "1987 [New preferred term]" or "2 (methoxyimino) 2 (quinuclidin 3-yl)acetonitrile hydrochloride" or "2 (nicotinamido)ethyl nitrate" or "2 acetyllactoyloxyethyl trimethylammonium 1,5 naphthalene disulfonate" or "2 carbamoyloxypropyltrimethylammonium chloride" or "2 ethyl 3-hydroxymethyl 4-(1-methyl-5-imidazolyl)butyric acid" or "2 ethyl 5-(1-methyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydro-5-pyridyl)-2H-tetrazole" or "2 ethyl 5-(1,2,3,6-tetrahydro-1-methyl-5-pyridyl)-2H-tetrazole" or "2 ethyl 5-(1,2,3,6-tetrahydro-1-methyl-5-pyridyl)-2H-tetrazole tartrate" or "2 ethyl 8-methyl-2,8-diazaspiro[4.5]decane 1,3-dione" or "2-methyl-4-dimethylaminomethyl-1,3-dioxolane" or "2-methyl-4-trimethylammoniomethyl-1,3-dioxolane" or "2-methyl-4-trimethylammoniummethyl-1,3-dioxolane" or "2-methyl-4-trimethylammoniummethyl-1,3-dioxolane iodide" or "2-methyl-5-[(dimethylamino)methyl]-1,3-oxathiolane methiodide" or "2-methyl-5-trimethylammoniomethyl-1,3-oxathiolane" or "2-methyl-5-trimethylammoniummethyl-1,3-oxathiolane" or "2-methyl-5-trimethylammoniummethyl-1,3-oxathiolane iodide" or "2-methylspiro[1-azabicyclo[2.2.2]octane-3,5'-[1,3]oxathiolane]" or "2-methylspiro[1,3-oxathiolane-5,3'-quinuclidine]" or "2-nicotinamidoethyl nitrate" or "2-nicotinoamidoethyl nitrate" or "2-(Acetyloxy)-N,N,N-trimethyl-1-propanaminium Chloride" or "2,7-dimethylthiochromine-8-ethanol" or "2,8-dimethyl-1,3-dioxo-8-azaspiro[4.5]decane" or "2,8-dimethyl-3-methylene-1-oxa-8-azaspiro[4.5]decane" or "2,8-dimethyl-3-methylene-1-oxa-8-azaspiro[4.5]decane tartrate monohydrate" or "2001 [Demotion of preferred term to synonym]" or "2-methylspiro(1,3-oxathiolane-5,3)quinuclidine" or "3-(2-diethylamino-2-methylpropylamino)-6-phenyl-5-propylpyridazine" or "3-(2-ethyl-2H-tetrazol-5-yl)-1,2,5,6-tetrahydro-1-methylpyridine" or "3-(2-morpholinoethylamino)benzocyclohepta[5,6-c]pyridazine" or "3-(2-propynyloxy)-1-azabicyclo[2.2.2]octane fumarate" or "3-(3-amino-1,2,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)-1-azabicyclo[2.2.2]octane" or "3-(3-amino-1,2,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)quinuclidine" or "3-(3-methyl-1,2,4-oxadiazol-5-yl)-1-azabicyclo[2.2.1]heptane" or "3-(3-oxo-2,8-diazaspiro[4.5]decan-8-yl)-8-azabicyclo[3.2.1]octane-8-carboxylic acid ethyl ester" or "3-(4-butylthio-1,2,5-thiadiazol-3-yl)-1-azabicyclo[2.2.2]octane" or "3-(4-butylthio-1,2,5-thiadiazol-3-yl)quinuclidine" or "3-(4-hexyloxy-1,2,5-thiadiazol-3-yl)-1,2,5,6-tetrahydro-1-methylpyridine" or "3-(6-chloro-2-pyrazinyl)-1-azabicyclo[2.2.2]octane" or "3-(6-chloro-2-pyrazinyl)-1-azabicyclo[2.2.2]octane maleate" or "3-(6-chloro-2-pyrazinyl)quinuclidine" or "3-[3-(3-methoxyphenyl)-2-propynyloxyimino]-1-azabicyclo[2.2.1]heptane" or "3-[4-(hexylthio)-1,2,5-thiadiazol-3-yl]-1,2,5,6-tetrahydro-1-methylpyridine" or "3-[N-(2-diethylamino-2-methylpropyl)amino]-6-phenyl-5-propylpyridazine sesquifumarate" or "3-acetoxy-1-benzyl-1-methylpyrrolidinium" or "3-acetoxy-1-benzyl-1-methylpyrrolidinium bromide" or "3-acetoxyquinuclidine" or "3-acetoxyquinuclidine" or "3-ethyl-4-[(1-methyl-1H-imidazol-5-yl)methyl]dihydrofuran-2(3H)-one" or "3-ethyl-4-[(3-methylimidazol-4-yl)methyl]oxolan-2-one" or "3-ethyl-4-[(1-methyl-1H-imidazol-5-yl)methyl]-2(3H)-furanone" or "3-formyl-5,6-dihydro-1(2H)-pyridinecarboxylic acid-4-chlorophenyl ester or methyloxime" or "3-propargyloxyquinuclidine fumarate" or "3-quinuclidinol acetate" or "3-quinuclidinyl acetate" or "3-(3-(3-fluoropropyl)thio)-1,2,5-thiadiazol-4-yl-1,2,5,6-tetrahydro-1-methylpyridine" or "3-(3-(3-butylthio)-1,2,5-thiadiazol-4-yl)-1,2,5,6-tetrahydro-1-methylpyridine" or "3-(3-butylthio)-1,2,5-thiadiazol-4-yl)-1,2,5,6-tetrahydro-1-methylpyridine oxalate" or "3-(3-

Muscarinic receptor agonists and positive allosteric modulators in animal models of psychosis: a systematic review and metaanalysis
Search strategy in MEDLINE via Ovid SP

butylthio-1,2,5-thiadiazol-4-yl)-1,2,5,6-tetrahydro-1-methylpyridine, 11C-labeled" or "3-(3-isoxazoloxy)-1-azabicyclo(2.2.2)octane" or "3-(3-O-hexyl-1,2,5-thiadiazol-4-yl)-1,2,5,6-tetrahydro-1-methylpyridine" or "3-(4-bromobenzoyl)-2-quinolinecarboxaldehyde" or "3alpha,16alpha eburnamonine" or "3-amino-5-chloro-6-methoxy-4-methyl-thieno(2,3-b)pyridine-2-carboxylic acid cyclopropylamide" or "3-amino-N-(4-methoxybenzyl)-4,6-dimethylthieno(2,3-b)pyridine-2-carboxamide" or "3H6 cells" or "4 aminomethyl 1 benzyl 2 pyrrolidinone" or "4 aminomethyl 1 benzyl 2 pyrrolidinone hydrogen fumarate" or "4 aminomethyl 1 phenylmethyl 2 pyrrolidinone" or "4 chlorophenyl 3 formyl 5,6 dihydro 1(2h) pyridinecarboxylate o methyloxime" or "4 dimethylaminomethyl 2 methyl 1,3 dioxolane" or "4-(3-(4-butylpiperidin-1-yl)propyl)-7-fluoro-4H-benzo(1,4)oxazin-3-one" or "4,4'-bis-((2,6-dichloro-benzyloxyimino)methyl)-1,1'-propane-1,3-diyl-bis-pyridinium" or "4,4'-bis-((2,6-dichloro-benzyloxy-imino)methyl)-1,1'-propane-1,3-diyl-bis-pyridinium dibromide" or "5 (2 ethyl 2h tetrazol 5 yl) 1 methyl 1,2,3,6 tetrahydropyridine" or "5 (2 ethyl 2h tetrazol 5 yl) 1,2,3,6 tetrahydro 1 methylpyridine" or "5 [(4 ethyl 2,3,4,5 tetrahydrofuran 5 on 3 yl)methyl] 1 methylimidazole" or "5 [(dimethylamino)methyl] 2 methyl 1,3 oxathiolane methiodide" or "5 [4 (hexylsulfanyl) 1,2,5 thiadiazol 3 yl] 1 methyl 1,2,3,6 tetrahydropyridine" or "5 dimethylaminomethyl 2 methyl 1,3 oxathiolane 3 oxide" or "5 methylfuron" or "5 methylfurfuryltrimethylammonium iodide" or "5 methylfurmethide" or "5 methylfurmethide iodide" or "6-(4-butylthio-1,2,5-thiadiazol-3-yl)-1-azabicyclo(3.2.1)octane" or "8 chloro 11 (1 piperaziny) 5h dibenzo[b,e][1,4]diazepine" or "8-chloro-11-piperazin-1-yl-5H-dibenzo(B,E)(1,4)diazepine" or "9-methoxy-9-methoxycarbonyl-8-methyl-2,3,9,10-tetrahydro-8,11-epoxy-1H,8H,11H-2,7b-11a-triazadibenzo(a,g)cycloocta(cde)-trinden-1-one" or "A 343, McNeil" or "abovis" or "AC260584" or "AC-260584" or "AC-42 amiodarone" or "acecholine" or Aceclidine* or "aceclydine" or "acecolex" or "acecolin" or "acecoline" or "acetyl tetramethylammonium chloride" or "Acetyl 2 methylcholine Chloride" or "acetyl beta metacholine" or "acetyl beta methylcholine" or "acetyl beta methylcholine chloride" or "acetyl choline" or "acetyl choline chloride" or "Acetyl-2-methylcholine Chloride" or "Acetyl-beta-methylcholine" or "acetylcholine" or "acetylcholine bromide" or "acetylcholine chloride" or "acetylcholine hydrochloride" or "acetylcholine,beta methyl" or "acetylcholine 1,5 naphthalenedisulfonate" or "acetylmethylcholine" or "acetonium napadisilate" or "adancor" or "adsorbocarpine" or "ae 37" or "ae37" or "af 102 b" or "af 102b" or "AF 102B, (cis-(+))-isomer" or "AF 102B, (trans)-isomer" or "af102b" or "AF-102B" or "AF267B" or "agn 190584" or "agn190584" or "ah 6405" or "ah6405" or "ahr 602" or "ahr602" or "akarpine" or "alemoxan" or "almocarpine" or "alpha (methoxyimino) 1 azabicyclo[2.2.2]octane 3 acetonitrile" or "alpha methoxyiminoquinclidine 3 acetonitrile" or Alvimeline or "amechol" or "AN2/AVex 73" or "AN2/AVex73" or "ana 001" or "ana001" or "anasclerol" or "anavex" or "anavex 2-73" or "anavex2-73" or "angicor" or "arecaidine methyl ester" or "arecaidine propargyl ester" or "Arecaline" or "Arecholin" or "Arecholine" or "Arecolin" or "arecoline" or "arecoline bromhydrate" or "arecoline bromide" or "arecoline hydrobromide" or "arecoline hydrochloride" or "arecolyne" or "arterocholine" or "arterocolin" or "arterocoline" or "asthenopin" or "atonyl" or "ausomina" or "avex 73" or "avex73" or "AZ13713945" or "azaleptin" or "AZD6088" or "benzoquinazolinone 12" or "beta methylacetylcholine" or "beta methylcholine carbamate" or "betacholyl" or "betanechol" or "betanechol chloride" or "betanechol sodium" or Bethanechol or "Bethanechol" or "betoptic pilo" or Blarcamesine or "bm 130" or "bm 5" or "bm130" or "bm5" or "BQCA" or Bromoacetylcholine or "bromoarecoline" or "brucine" or "brucine N-oxide" or "bruzin" or "BuTAC cpd" or "butyl trimethyl ammonium bromide" or "butylthio-TZTP" or Butyltrimethylammonium or "butyrocholine" or "butyryl choline" or Butyrylcholine or "cacholitin" or Carbachol* or "carbammann" or "carbamed" or "carbamine choline" or "carbaminocholine" or "carbaminocholine chloride" or "carbaminoylcholine" or

Muscarinic receptor agonists and positive allosteric modulators in animal models of psychosis: a systematic review and metaanalysis
Search strategy in MEDLINE via Ovid SP

"carbamoylcholine" or "carbamoylcholine chloride" or "carbamoylmethylcholine chloride" or "carbamy beta methylcholine" or "carbamy choline" or "carbamy choline" or "carbamy choline chloride" or "carbamy methylcholine" or "carbamy methylcholine chloride" or "carbostat" or "carbocholine" or "carbolin" or "carboptic" or "carcholin" or "ceb 242" or "ceb242" or "cebralart" or "cendo carpine" or "cerebroxine" or "ceredia" or "Cervoxan" or "cetal" or "cetal retard" or Cevimeline or "cholentyl" or "choline 1,5 naphthalenedisulfonate dilactate diacetate" or "choline acetate" or "choline acetate lactate 1,5 naphthalenedisulfonate" or "choline acetylate" or "choline butyrate" or "choline chloride carbamate" or "cholinergol" or "choryl" or "ci 979" or "ci979" or "CID 42633508" or "cis 2 methyl 5 [(dimethylamino)methyl] 1,3 oxathiolane methiodide" or "clopine" or "clopsine" or "clozapin" or "Clozapine" or "Clozaril" or "coletyl" or "CS 932" or "CS-932" or "CVL-231" or "dancor" or "decincan" or "demethylclozapine" or "denzapine" or "desmethylclozapine" or "devincal" or "devincan" or "devinkan" or "dimethoxystrychnine" or "dimethylethyl(2 hydroxyethyl)ammonium chloride benzilate" or "dimethyl-W 84" or "dimethyl-W84" or "dorlen" or "dorval" or "doryl" or "dozapine" or "dropilton" or "Duo3" or "Duo3 cpd" or "duracholine" or "duvoid" or "e 3" or "e pilo" or "e pilo 2" or "eburnal" or "eburnal ritardo" or "eburnamonine" or "eburnan 16 one" or "eburnane,14 oxo" or "elcrit" or Emraclidine or "enbornoxin" or "ens 163" or "ens163" or "enterotonin" or "epinephrine/aceclidine" or "epinephrine-aceclidine" or "equiton" or "esberidin" or "ethyl 3 (3 oxo 2,8 diazaspiro[4.5]decan 8 yl) 8 azabicyclo[3.2.1]octane 8 carboxylate" or "ethyl 3-(4-(6-fluoro-2-oxo-2,3-dihydro-1H-benzimidazol-1-yl)piperidin-1-yl)pyrrolidine-1-carboxylate" or "evoxac" or "fazaclo" or "fazaclo odt" or "fks 508" or "fks508" or "FKS-508" or "fotil" or "fotil forte" or "fotil sine" or "FP-TZTP" or "furfuryltrimethylammonium" or "Furmethide" or "furthretonium" or "furtrethonium" or "furtrimethonium" or "glaucadrin" or "glaucadrine" or "glaucocarpine" or "glaucomil" or "glaucostat" or "glaumarin" or "HDMPPA" or Heptyltrimethylammonium or "hexamethylene 1,6 bis(dimethyl(3 phthalimidopropyl)ammonium bromide]" or "hexamethylenebis(dimethyl-(3-phthalimidopropyl)ammonium bromide)" or "hf 1854" or "hf1854" or "hormotonin" or "HTL0016878" or "HTL0018318" or "HTL9936" or "icr 170 g" or "ikorel" or "iperoxo" or "iricoline" or Isoarecaidine or "isoarecoline" or "isopilocarpate" or Isopilocarpic Acid or Isopilocarpine or "isopto carpina" or "isopto carpine" or "isopto karbakolin" or "isoptocarbachol" or "isoptocarpine" or "isoptopilocarpine" or Itameline or "jestryl" or "k 252" or "k 252a" or "K 252b" or "K 252c" or "K 252d" or "k252a" or "karbakolin" or "karbakolin isopto" or "kss 694" or "kss694" or "KT 5720" or "KT 5823" or "KT5720" or "KT5823" or "l 660863" or "l 689660" or "l eburnamonine" or Lachesine or "lapenax" or "lentichol" or "lentin" or "lentivasan" or "lentyl" or "Leponex" or "levo eburnamonine" or "liberon" or "liocarpina" or "lozapin" or "lozapine" or "lu 25 109" or "lu 25 109 t" or "lu 25 109m" or "lu 25 109t" or "lu 25109" or "lu 25109 t" or "lu 25109m" or "lu 25109t" or "lu25 109" or "lu25 109 t" or "lu25 109m" or "lu25 109t" or "lu25109" or "lu25109 t" or "lu25109m" or "lu25109t" or "lumeron" or "lx 100 129" or "lx100129" or "ly 246708" or "ly 287041" or "ly 297802" or "LY 593093" or "LY2033298" or "LY2119620" or "LY246708" or "LY-246708" or "ly287041" or "ly297802" or "LY593093" or "McN A 343" or "McN A343" or "McN A-343" or "McNA343" or "McN-A343" or "McN-A-343" or "McNeil A 343" or "mecholin" or "Mecholine" or "mecholy" or "mecothane" or "memcor" or "memolog" or "memric" or "metacholine" or "metacholine chloride" or Methacholine or "methacholinium" or "methychol" or "methyl 1 methyl delta3,4 tetrahydro 3 pyridinecarboxylate" or "methyl 1,2,5,6 tetrahydro 1 methylnicotinate" or "methyl n methyltetrahydronicotinate" or "methylacetylcholine" or "Methylarecaidin" or "methylfurmethide" or "methylfurmetide" or Methylfurtrethonium or Milameline or "minorin" or "minorine" or "miocarpine" or "miocarpine smp" or "miochol" or "miochol e" or "miochol-e system pak" or "miochol-

Muscarinic receptor agonists and positive allosteric modulators in animal models of psychosis: a systematic review and metaanalysis
Search strategy in MEDLINE via Ovid SP

e/steri-tags" or "miocholine" or "miostat" or "miotonoachol" or "miovisin" or "mj 13653" or "mj13653" or "MK-7622" or "ML129" or "ML169" or "ML380" or "moryl" or "muscaran" or Muscarone or "myo hermes" or "myocholine" or "myocholine glenwood" or "myotonachol" or "myotonine" or "myotonine chloride" or "mytonoachol" or "n (2 hydroxyethyl)nicotinamide nitrate" or "n (2 nitrateethyl)nicotinamide" or "n (2 pyrimidinyl)piperazine" or "n [2 (1 azabicyclo[3.3.0]octan 5 yl)ethyl] 2 nitroaniline fumarate" or "n [2 (nitrooxy)ethyl] 3 pyridinecarboxamide" or "n benzyl 3 pyrrolidyl acetate" or "n benzyl 3 pyrrolidyl acetate methobromide" or "n benzyl 3 pyrrolidylacetate" or "n benzyl 3 pyrrolidylacetate methobromide" or "n butyryl choline" or "n heptyl trimethylammonium iodide" or "n methyl 1,2,5,6 tetrahydroisonicotinic acid" or "n methyl 1,2,5,6 tetrahydropyridine 3 carboxylic acid methyl ester" or "n methyl n (1 methyl 4 pyrrolidino 2 butynyl)acetamide" or "n methyl n [1 methyl 4 (1 pyrrolidiny) 2 butyn 1 yl]acetamide" or "n methyl n [5 (1 pyrrolidiny) 3 pentyn 2 yl]acetamide" or "n norclozapine" or "N-(3-hydroxytetrahydro-2H-pyran-4-yl)-5-methyl-4-(4-(1,3-thiazol-4-yl)benzyl)pyridine-2-carboxamide" or "N-(6-((1-((4-fluorobenzyl)(methyl)amino)ethylidene))amino)-2-hydroxy-2,3-dihydro-1H-inden-1-ylbiphenyl-4-carboxamide" or "N,N'-bis(3-(1,3-dihydro-1,3-dioxo-4-methyl-2H-isoindol-2-yl)propyl)-N,N,N',N'-tetramethyl-1,6-hexanediaminium diiodide" or "N-benzyl brucine" or "N-chloromethylbrucine" or "N-chloromethyl-brucine" or "N-desmethylclozapine" or Nebracetam or "NGX267" or "nnc 11 0232" or "nnc 11 1053" or "nnc 111053" or "NNC 11-1314" or "NNC 11-1585" or "NNC 11-1607" or "nnc11 1053" or "NNC111314 OR phenylpropargyloxy-1,2,5-thiadiazole-quinuclidine OR NNC-11-1314 " or "NNC111607" or "NNC-11-1607" or "nooxine" or "norclozapine" or "o acetyl beta methylcholine chloride" or "o.p.d." or "obisot" or "ocu vinc" or "ocucarpine" or "ocu-carpine" or "ocuser" or "ocuser 20" or "ocuser 40" or "ocuser p 20" or "ocuser p-40" or "ocuser pilo" or "ocuser pilo 20" or "ocuser pilo-40" or "ocuvinc" or "oftan pilocarpin" or "oq-miot" or "ovisort" or "ovisot" or "oxa 22" or "oxotremorin" or "Oxotremorine" or "oxygeron" or "oxytremorin" or "oxytremorine" or "p.v. carpine" or "p.v. carpine liquifilm" or "p.v. carpine liquifilm ophthalmic solution" or "pd 129409" or "pd129409" or "pentylthio-TZTP" or "perisasol" or "pervincamine" or "pervone" or "PF-06767832" or "PF-06827443" or "pil ofteno" or "piladren" or "pilagan" or "pilagan with c cap" or "pilaren" or "pilasite" or "pilo grin" or "pilobuc" or "pilocar" or "pilocarpate" or "Pilocarpic Acid" or "pilocarpin" or Pilocarpine or "pilocarpinium chloride" or "pilocarpol" or "pilofrin" or "pilogel" or "pilogel hs" or "piloheptine" or "pilocarpin isopto" or "pilocarpin minims" or "pilomann" or "pilomin" or "pilomiotin" or "pilopine" or "pilopine hs" or "pilopine hs gel" or "pilopt" or "pilopt eye drops" or "piloptic" or "piloptic-1" or "piloptic-1/2" or "piloptic-2" or "piloptic-3" or "piloptic-4" or "piloptic-6" or "pilostat" or "pilosyst" or "pilotonina" or "PPBI compound" or "pragmoline" or "Propionylcholine Iodide" or "provocholine" or "Provokit" or "PT-1284" or "pyrrolidyl piperidyl benzimidazolinone" or Revosimeline or "rp 46417" or "rp46417" or "ru 35926" or "ru 47213" or "ru35926" or "ru47213" or Sabcomeline or "salagen" or "saligren" or "samonyl" or "sandoz ens 163" or "sandoz ens163" or "sanpilo" or "sb 202026" or "sb 202026a" or "sb202026" or "sb202026a" or "sdz ens 163" or "sdz ens163" or "sf 2370" or "sf2370" or "sg 75" or "sg75" or "sigmart" or "sizopin" or "skf 100916 j" or "SNI 2011" or "SNI-2011" or "sno pilo" or "sodium 1-(4-methoxybenzyl)-4-oxo-1,4-dihydroquinoline-3-carboxylate" or "spersacarpine" or "SPP1" or "sr 46559" or "sr 46559 a" or "sr 46559a" or "staurosporine aglycone" or "strychnine" or "strychnidin 10 one" or "strychnine" or "T-495" or "TAK-071" or Talsaclidine or "taurosporine" or Tazomeline or "tetrahydro n,n dimethyl 2,2 diphenyl 3 furanmethanamine" or "thiochrome" or Thiopilocarpine or "tm 723" or "tonifor" or "tonocholin" or "tonocholine" or "tp ophthal" or "tremorin" or Tremorine or "trimethylheptylammonium" or "tripervan" or "ucholine" or "uninechol" or "urecholine" or "urecholine chloride" or "urocarb" or "urotone" or "urotonine" or Vedaclidine or "versacloz"

Muscarinic receptor agonists and positive allosteric modulators in animal models of psychosis: a systematic review and metaanalysis
Search strategy in MEDLINE via Ovid SP

- or "vinburnine" or "vinca hexal" or "vincalen" or "vincamax" or "vincamed" or "vincamin" or "vincamine" or "vincamine hydrochloride" or "vincamone" or "vincapan" or "vincapront" or "vincarosa" or "vincaryl" or "vincimax" or "vistacarpin" or "vitacarpine" or "vraap" or "VU 0405652" or "VU0010010" or "VU0029767" or "VU0090157" or "VU0119498" or "VU0152099" or "VU0152100" or "VU0238429" or "VU0405652" or "VU0453595" or "VU0467154" or "VU0467485" or "VU0476406" or "VU0486846" or "VU319" or "VU6003130" or "VU6004256" or "w 84" or "w84" or "W-84" or "wal 2014" or "wal 2014 fu" or "wander compound" or "Wduo3" or "web 1881" or "web 1881 fu" or "web1881" or "web1881 fu" or "wecoli" or "WIN 62,577" or Xanomeline or "ximex opticar" or "ym 796" or "ym796" or "zapen" or "zaponex" or "zhenrui").ti,ab,tw.
3. Muscarinic Agonists/ or Muscarine/ or (Muscarin or Muscarine or Muscarinic or M1 or M2 or M3 or M4 or M5 or Muscarinomimetic*).ti,ab,tw. (290751)
 4. Allosteric Regulation/ or Allosteric Site/ or (Alloster* or PAM or PAMs or Modulat* or Agonis*).ti,ab,tw.
 5. 3 and 4
 6. exp animal experimentation/ or exp models, animal/ or Animals/ or exp animal population groups/ or chordata/ or vertebrates/ or exp amphibians/ or exp birds/ or exp fishes/ or exp reptiles/ or mammals/ or primates/ or eutheria/ or exp artiodactyla/ or exp carnivore/ or exp cephalopoda/ or exp cetacea/ or exp chiroptera/ or exp elephants/ or exp hyraxes/ or exp insectivora/ or exp lagomorpha/ or exp marsupialia/ or exp monotremata/ or exp perissodactyla/ or Proboscidea Mammal/ or exp rodentia/ or exp scandentia/ or exp sirenia/ or exp cingulata/ or haplorhini/ or exp strepsirhini/ or exp platyrrhini/ or exp tarsii/ or catarrhini/ or exp cercopithecidae/ or exp hylobatidae/ or hominidae/ or exp gorilla gorilla/ or exp pan paniscus/ or exp pan troglodytes/ or exp pongo/ or (aardvark* or acanthuridae or acanthuriformes or acanthurus or acinonyx or acipenser* or adder* or aepyceros or afrosoricida or afrotheria or agama or agamidae or agapornis or agkistrodon or ailuridae or aix or alauda or albifrons or alcelaphinae or alectoris or aethinophidia or alligator or alligatoridae or alligators or allobates or alouatta or alouattinae or alpaca* or alytes or alytidae or amazona or ambystoma or ambystomatidae or ameiurus or ammodytes or amniote* or amphibia* or amphiuma or amphiumidae or anabantiformes or anas or anaxyrus or anchovies or anchovy or anguis fragilis or animal* or anodorhynchus or anolis or anser* or anteater* or antelope* or anthropoid* or antilope* or antilopinae or anura or aotidae or aotus or aoudad or ape or apes or apodemus or apteronotus or ara or araneus or arapaima or aras or archosaur or ariidae or arius or armadillo* or artiodactyla or arvicolinae or ateles or atelidae or atelinae or athene noctua or atheriniformes or atherinopsidae or auratus or aurochs or aves or avian* or aythya or baboon* or badger* or bagridae or balaenoptera or bandicoot* or banteng or barbel* or barbus or bass or bat or batrachoidiformes or bats or bear or bearded dragon* or bears or beaver* or beloniformes or bewickii or bighead gobies or bighead goby or bird* or bison* or bitis or blackbird* or blackbuck* or blue tit or blue tits or blue whiting* or bluethroat* or boar* or bobwhite* or boidae or bombina* or bonobo* or boreoeutheria or bos or bothrops or anguilla or bovid or bovine or bowfin* or brachyteles or branta or bream or brill or brotula barbata or bubalus or buck or bucks or budgerigar or buffalo* or bufo or bufonidae or bufotes or bull* or ewe or bungarus or bush babies or bush baby or bushbab* or buteo or buzzard* or caiman* or cairina or calamita or calf or calidris or callicebus or callimico or callithrix or callitrichinae or calloselasma or calves or camel* or canaria* or canary or canidae or caniformia or canine* or canis or canutus or capra* or caprinae or caprine or capybara* or carangaria incertae sedis or carassius or carcharhiniformes or caretta or carnivora or carp or carpio or carps or carus or castor canadensis or castor fiber or cat or catarrhini or catfish* or catostom* or cats or catshark* or cattle or catus or cavia or cebidae

Muscarinic receptor agonists and positive allosteric modulators in animal models of psychosis: a systematic review and metaanalysis
Search strategy in MEDLINE via Ovid SP

or cebuella or cebus or centrarchidae or centrarchiformes or centropomidae or cephalopod* or cerastes or cercocebus or cercopithec* or cervus or cetacea or chamois or channa or char or characi* or charadriiformes or chars or cheirogaleidae or chelonia or chick* or chimpanzee* or chinchilla* or chipmunk* or chiroptera or chlorocebus or chondrosteian or chordata or chroicocephalus or chub or chubs or cichlid* or cingulata or circus or cirrhinus or clarias or clariidae or clupea or clupeidae or clupeiformes or cob or cobiti* or cockatiel or cockatoo* or cod or cods or coelacanth or colinus or colobinae or colobus or colubridae or columba or columbianus or columbidae or columbiformes or common bleak* or common chaffinch* or common chiffchaff* or common dab* or common dace* or common dragonet* or common ling* or common moorhen* or common nase* or common redstart* or common roach* or common rudd* or common sandpiper* or common sole or common soles or common whitethroat* or coregon* or corvidae or corvus or corydoras or cottidae or cottonrat* or cottus or coturnix or cow or cows or coyote* or crecca or cricetinae or cricetulus or cricetus or crocidura or crocod* or crotalinae or crotalus or crow or crows or culaea or cuneata or cuniculidae or cuniculus or curema or cuttlefish* or cyanistes or cygnet or cygnus or cynoglossus or cynomolgus or cynomys or cynops or cypriniformes or cyprinodon* or cyprinus or daboia or danio or dasycneme or dasyproctidae or daubentonii or decapodiformes or deer or deinagkistrodon or dendroaspis or dendrobatidae or dermoptera or desmodus or diapsid or dicentrarchus or diglossidae or didelphimorphia or didelphis or dipodomys or diprotodontia or diptera* or discoglossus or dog or dogfish* or dogs or dolphin* or donkey* or dormice or dormouse or doryteuthis or dosidicus or douroucoulis or dove or dover sole* or doves or drake* or dromaiidae or dromaius novaehollandiae or dromedar* or drosophilidae or duck or duckling* or ducks or dugong* or duttaphrynus or eagle* or echidna* or echis or eel or eelpout* or eels or eigenmannia or eland* or elaphus or elapidae or elasmobranch* or electrophorus or elephant* or elver* or emberizidae or emu or emus or epidalea or epinephelus or eptesicus or equidae or equine or equus or eretmochelys or erithacus or ermine* or erythrocebus or esocidae or esociformes or esox or estrilidae or euarchontoglires or eupleridae or eurasian blackcap* or eurasian coot* or eurasian jays or eurasian wigeon* or garganey or eurasian woodcock* or european hake* or european smelt* or european sprat* or eutheria or ewes or falco sparverius or falcon* or fascicularis or felidae or feliformia or feline* or felis or mink or ferina or ferret* or ficedula or filly or finch or fingerling* or fish or fishes or fitch* or fitchew or flatfish* or flounder* or flycatcher or fowl* or fox or foxes or frog* or fuligula or fundulidae or fundulus or furnariidae or gadiformes or gadus or gadwall* or galagidae or galago* or trachemys or galaxias or galaxiidae or galaxiiformes or galliformes or gallopavo or gallus or gambusia or gander or gar or garfish* or garganeys or gariepinus or gars or gasterosteus or gaur or gavialidae or gavialis or gazelle* or geese or geopelia or gerbil* or gibbon* or gibbosus or gilt or giraffe* or glama or glareolus or glires or gloydus or goat or goats or gobbler* or gobiocypris or godwit* or goldfish* or goose or gopher* or gorilla* or gosling* or graylag* or great cormorant* or great knot* or great tit* or greater pipefish* or grey gurnard* or grey heron* or greylag or grouse or grus or guanaco or gudgeon or guineafowl or gull or gulls or gulo or guppies or guppy or guttata or gymnophiona or gymnotiformes or gymnotus or haddock* or haematopus or hagfish* or halibut or halichoerus or hamster* or hapale or haplorhini or hare or harengus or hares or harrier* or hartebeest* or hogget or hawk or hawks or hedgehog* or heifer or hemachatus or hen or hens or herpestidae or herring* or heteropneustes or heteropneustidae or hippopotamidae or hippopotamus or hog or hogs or hollandicus or holocephali or hominid* or hominoidea or hoolock* or hoplobatrachus or horse* or hyaenidae or hydrophiidae or hyla or hylidae or hylobates or hylobatidae or hypoleuca or hypophthalmichthys or hyrax* or ibex* or ictaluridae or ictalurus or ide or

Muscarinic receptor agonists and positive allosteric modulators in animal models of psychosis: a systematic review and metaanalysis
Search strategy in MEDLINE via Ovid SP

iguana* or iguanidae or impala* or in vivo or indriidae or insectivora or jackal or jackdaw or jackdaws or jaculus or jerboa or jerboas or jird or jirds or kangaroo* or killifish or koala* or labeo or labrax or cyprinidae or lachesis or laevis or lagomorph or lagomorpha or lagopus or lama or lamas or lamb or lambs or lampetra or lamprey or lampreys or lapponica or laprine or lapwing or lapwings or larimichthys or lateolabracidae or lateolabrax or lates or laticauda or latimeria or laurasiatheria or lemming or lemmings or lemmus or lemon sole or lemon soles or lemur or lemuridae or lemurs or leontopithecus or lepidosaur or lepomis or leporidae or leptodactylidae or leptodactylus or lepus or lesser weever or lesser weevers or lesser whitethroat or lesser whitethroats or leuciscus or leucopsis or leucoraja or leucorodia or leveret or limosa or lion or lions or lissotriton or litoria or lizard or lizards or llama or llamas or loligo or longspined bullhead or longspined bullheads or lophocebus or loriciariidae or loris or loridae or lucioperca or lullula or lungfish or lungfishes or lusciniidae or lutra or lynx or lynxes or macaca* or macaque* or macaw or macaws or mackerel or mackerels or macropodidae or macropus or macrovipera or magpie or magpies or mallard or mallards or mammal or mammals or mammoth or mammoths or mandrillus or marmoset* or marmot or marmota or marmots or marsupial or marsupialia or marsupials or marten or martens or martes or megalobrama or megrim or meleagris or meles or melopsittacus or menidia or mephitidae or merione or meriones or merula or mesocricetus or mice or microhylidae or micropogonias or micropterus or microtus or micrurus or minks or minnow or minnows or misgurnus or mithun or mole or moles or monedula or monkey* or monodelphis or monotremata or monotremate or morhua or morone or mouflon or mouflons or mouse or mugil or mulatta or mule or mules or mullet or mullets or muntjac or muntjacs or muridae or murinae or murine or mus or muscipidae or musculus or muskox or muskrat or muskrats or mustela or mustelidae or mustelus or mylopharyngodon or myodes or myotis or myoxidae or naja or nandiniidae or nautilus or necturus or newt or newts or nomascus or northern shoveler or northern wheatear or northern wheatears or norvegicus or norway pout or norway pouts or norwegian topknot or notophthalmus or numida or nymphicus or octodon or octopodiformes or octopus or octopuses or odontophoridae or odorrana or oncorhynchus or ophiophagus or opossum or opossums or orang utan or orang utans or orangutan or orangutans or oreochromis or oryctolagus or oryzias or osmeriformes or osmerus or osphronemidae or osteoglossidae or osteoglossiformes or osteolaemus or ostralegus or ostrich or ostriches or otter or otters or ovine or ovis or salmonid or owl or owls or oystercatcher or oystercatchers or paddlefish or paddlefishes or paenungulata or pagrus or palaeognathae or pan paniscus or pan troglodytes or panda or pandas or pandion or panthera or papio or parakeet or parakeets or paralichthyidae or paralichthys or paramisgurnus or paridae or parrot or parrots or parus or passer domesticus or passeridae or passeriformes or pelamis or pelobates fuscus or pelobatidae or pelodiscus or pelophylax or pelteobagrus fulvidraco or pempheriformes or penguin or penguins or perca or perch or perches or percidae or perciformes or perdicinae or perdix or perissodactyla or peromyscus or petromyzon or phalangeridae or phascolarctidae or phasianidae or philomachus or phoca or phocoena or phodopus or pholidota or phyllomedusa or phyllostomidae or pig or pigeon* or piglet or piglets or pigs or pike or pikes or pimelodidae or pimephales or pintail or pintails or pipidae or pipistrelle or pipistrellus or pisces or pitheciidae or plaice or platalea or platessa or platichthys or platypus or platyrrhini or pleurodeles or pleuronectes or pleuronectidae or plover or plovers or poacher or poachers or pochard or poecilia or poecilia reticulata or poeciliidae or poeciliopsis gracilis or pogona or polecat* or pollock or pollocks or pongidae or pongo or porcellus or porcine or porcupine or porcupines or porpoise or porpoises or potoroidae or potoroo or potoroos or poultries or poultry or pouting or presbytini or primate or primates or proboscidea or procyonidae or

Muscarinic receptor agonists and positive allosteric modulators in animal models of psychosis: a systematic review and metaanalysis
Search strategy in MEDLINE via Ovid SP

promelas or prosimian or prosimians or proteidae or proteus or protobothrops or psetta or pseudacris or psittaciformes or psittacine or psittacula or pterocnemis or pteropus or pugnax or puma or pumas or pumpkinseed or pungitius or putorius or pygerythrus or python or pythonidae or pythons or quail or quails or rabbit* or raccoon or raccoons or ram or rana or ranas or ranidae or raptor or raptors or rat or ratite or rats or rattus or raven or ravens or red junglefowl or red knot or red knots or red sea sailfin tang or red-backed shrike or red-backed shrikes or redshank or redshanks or reindeer or reptile or reptiles or reptilia or rerio or rhea or rheiformes or rhinella or rhynchocephalia or ridibundus or risoria or robin or robins or rodent or rodentia or rodents or rook or rooks or lasiurus or rosy bitterling* or round gobies or round goby or rousettus or ruddy turnstone* or sheatfish or ruff or ruminant* or rupicapra or russell's viper* or russula or rutilus or sable or sables or saguinus or saimiri or saimiriinae or saithe or saithes or salamander or salamanders or salamandra or salamandridae or salientia or salmo or salmon or salmonidae or salmonids or salmonids or salmoniformes or salmonine or salmons or salvadora or salvelinus or sand smelt or sand smelts or sander or sanderling or sanderlings or sapajus or sardine or sardines or sarotherodon or sauropsid or scaldfish or scandentia or sciaenidae or sciuridae or sciurus or scophthalmidae or scophthalmus or scorpaeniformes or scrofa or sculpin or scyliorhinus or seabass or seabasses or seabird or seabirds or seahorse or seahorses or seal or seals or sebastes or sebastidae or sepia or sepiella or serinus or serotinus or shark or sharks or sheatfishes or sheep or shelduck or shelducks or shorebird or shorebirds or shrew* or siamang or siamangs or sigmodon or sigmodontinae or siluridae or siluriformes or silurus or simian or simians or sipunculida or sirenia or skylark or skylarks or sloth or sloths or smegmamorpha or smolt or smolts or snake* or snakehead or snakeheads or solea or soleidae or solenette or song thrush or song thrushes or songbird or songbirds or sores or sow or sows or spalax or spariformes or sparrow or sparrows or sparus or spermophilus or spheniscidae or sphenodon or spoonbill or spoonbills or squalus or squamate or squid or squirrel* or starling or starlings or starry smooth-hound or starry smooth-hounds or stenella or sterna or stickleback or sticklebacks or stingray or stingrays or stizostedion or stone loach or stone loaches or strepsirhini or streptopelia or strigiformes or struthio camelus or struthioniformes or sturgeon or sturgeons or sturnus or sunfish or sunfishes or sus or suslik or susliks or swallow or swallows or swan or swans or swine* or sylvilagus or symphalangus or syncerus or syngnathidae or syngnathiformes or tachysurus or tadorna or tadpole or tadpoles or taeniopygia or takifugu or takin or talpa or tamarin or tamarins or tarsier or tarsii or tarsiidae or tarsiiform or teal or teals or teleost* or tench or tenches or tenrec or tenrec or tern or terrapin or tetrao or tetraodon or tetraodontiformes or tetrapod or tetrapods or thamnophilidae or theria or therian or theropithecus or tiger or tigers or tilapia or tilapias or tinca or toad or toads or todarodes or tomistoma or tompot blennies or tompot blenny or torpedo or tortoise or tortoises or tragelaphus or treeshrew or treeshrews or triakidae or trichechus or trichogaster or trichosurus or trimeresurus or trionyx or triturus or troglodytes or trout* or tub gurnards or tubulidentata or tuna or tupaia or tupaiidae or turbot or turbot or turdidae or turdus or turkeys or turtle* or twait shad or tyranni or tyrannidae or umbridae or unguiculatus or urodela or ursidae or vanellus or vendace or vertebrate* or vervet or vervets or vespertilionidae or vipera or viperidae or virginianus or vitticeps or vitulina or viverridae or vole or voles or vulpes or vulture or vultures or wallabia or wallaby or walrus or walruses or warbler or warblers or water rail or water rails or waterfowl or weasel or weasels or whale or whales or whinchat or whinchats or whitefish or whitefishes or whiting or whittings or wildebeest or wolf or wolverine or wolverines or wolves or woodlark or woodlarks or woodmice or woodmouse or woodpecker or woodpeckers or wryneck or wrynecks or xenarthra or xenopus or xiphophorus or yak or yaks or yellow boxfish or yellow boxfishes

Muscarinic receptor agonists and positive allosteric modulators in animal models of psychosis: a systematic review and metaanalysis
Search strategy in MEDLINE via Ovid SP

or zander or zanders or zebra* or zebu or zenaida or zonotrichia leucophrys).ti,ab.
(9333008)

7. 1 and (2 or 5) and 6